

MEASURING THE LEVEL OF CRITICAL THINKING ABILITY OF THE STUDENTS USING WATSON – GLASER APPRAISAL

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ABSTRACT

The study measures the level of critical thinking ability of students in terms of argument, assumptions, deduction, interpretation, and interference from the perspective of senior high school students from Valencia National High School, Valencia City High School, Paramount School of Arts, Languages, Management, and Sciences, Inc., and STI College – Valencia. The study employed a descriptive method. The study involved 137 senior high school students from different institutions who accomplished the 59-item assessment instrument based on the Watson – Glaser Critical Thinking Test. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The results revealed that the extent of the critical thinking ability of senior high school students is low. This implies that the critical thinking ability of senior high school students is relatively low in the different parts of the test. Results further suggest the level of critical thinking ability of students in terms of argument, assumptions, deduction, interpretation, and interference must be improved and go beyond mere recollection, recognize presumptions, and take into account other points of view.

Keywords: *Critical Thinking, Argument, Assumption, Interpretation, Inference, Deduction*

INTRODUCTION

Critical thinking is an analytical process that involves drawing conclusions, analyzing, explaining, and disputing while also developing one's cognitive processes. It also involves concluding pertinent evidence (Supriyatno, Susilawati, & Hassan, 2020). However, educational systems often need to cultivate these abilities in students adequately.

To effectively traverse the complicated nature of the 21st century, students must cultivate critical thinking abilities. The absence of emphasis on critical thinking techniques in educational institutions has been noted as a major barrier. According to research by Velayati et al. (2020), rote memorization and little exposure to different viewpoints cause pupils to frequently fail when trying to apply critical thinking skills in reading. In a similar vein, Aydin et al. (2023) suggest that there may be a discrepancy between curriculum goals and real classroom procedures, wherein critical thinking is not deliberately promoted.

Motivation and involvement among students present another difficulty. Critical thinking skills can be hampered by passive learning techniques and a lack of personal interest in the subject matter, according to research by Lopez et al. (2022). This is consistent with research by Chen et al. (2021), which found a link between students' growth in critical thinking and autonomy. Students are more inclined to think critically if they feel free to investigate subjects and pose questions. The cognitive biases and limits of students themselves can also be problematic. Critical thinking might be hampered by unconscious biases and the fear of being incorrect, according to a study by Osman (2020).

The study by Putri (2014), using critical thinking standards, revealed that the students needed to answer questions related to clarity, accuracy, precision, logic, and relevance. Moreover, it also shows that the students need help understanding the writer's position and reading between the lines. These findings concluded that the critical thinking ability of the students is weak. Velayati et al. (2017) also revealed that the students got the lowest scores on the critical thinking ability questionnaire. It also emphasized that critical thinking is difficult for them.

In this study, the researchers aim to measure the level of student's critical thinking using the different dimensions of the Watson - Glazer critical thinking test, specifically in terms of arguments, assumptions, deductions, interpretations, and inferences.

Research Questions

This research focuses on measuring the level of critical thinking skills of the students through Watson - Glazer Critical Thinking Test. Specifically, the study attempts to answer the following points:

1. What are level of student's critical thinking ability in terms of:
 - a. Argument;

- b. Assumption;
- c. Deduction;
- d. Interpretation and;
- e. Inference?

METHODOLOGY

This quantitative research utilized descriptive design to assess the critical thinking ability of the students. The study is conducted at Paramount School of Arts, Languages, Management, and Sciences, Inc., Valencia National High School, Valencia City High School, and STI College – Valencia. The respondents were 137 senior high school students from the abovementioned schools in Valencia City, Bukidnon.

Table 1: Scale description of Watson – Glaser Critical Thinking Test

Scale	Placement of	Scale Description
Argument	4 statement 14 Indicators	This critical thinking will assess your ability to reason logically when analyzing arguments.
Assumption	4 statement 13 Indicators	This critical thinking test will assess your ability to make logically justified assumption based upon the statement provided.
Deduction	4 Statement 12 Indicators	This critical thinking test will assess your ability to deduce information and reason logically using the
Interpretation	4 Statement 12 Indicators	This critical thinking test will assess your ability to interpret information into logical conclusions based upon the statement provided.
Inference	2 Statement 8 indicators	Is a conclusion drawn from observed or supposed facts.

This study utilized the Watson-Glaser Critical Thinking Appraisal designed to assess a person's critical thinking abilities. The questionnaires had an internal consistency reliability (Cronbach alpha coefficient) of 0.85 through pilot testing, which indicated good consistency and high reliability. The instrument used a scale to estimate the data from the participants. The data collected will be analyzed using descriptive statistics.

The evaluation of student's critical thinking test is determined by the table above. The argument will determine the ability to know how to make important decisions. It is important to distinguish the ability to argue. The assumption will determine the student's critical thinking, which is presupposed or taken for granted. The deduction will determine the student's capability to reason logically. The interpretation will determine whether the

students will assume all information in the passage and follow beyond a reasonable doubt from the information. The inference was determined by observing the information. It is important to know the student's observations and understanding.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Overall Mean Scores of the Different CT tests

<i>Critical Thinking Tests</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
Argument Test	52	Needs Improvement
Assumption Test	53	Needs Improvement
Deduction Test	73	Good
Interpretation Test	48	Poor
Inference Test	48	Poor
<i>Average</i>	55	Needs Improvement

Legends:

<i>Range</i>	<i>Description</i>
1 – 39	Very Poor
40 – 49	Poor
50 – 59	Needs Improvement
60 – 69	Satisfactory
70 – 79	Good
80 - 89	Very Good
90 – 100	Excellent

A. Argument Test

The results revealed that the average score of all the statements is 52 over 100 that indicates “needs improvement”. This implies that many students struggles with their argumentation skill especially on deciding which one weak or strong argument is. Identifying whether it is a strong or a weak arguments, it requires analyzing each arguments if it is both important and directly related to the statement and question. With this almost half of the students find it hard to assess the trivial aspect of the arguments and they are confused with the correlation of causation.

According to the study of Rusmini, Suyono, and Agustini (2021), many students are aware of their shortcomings in analyzing argumentation skill questions. Based on the analysis of the data obtained, students have not been able to give a strong reason for an argument and draw a conclusion well. In a similar study of Landrieu, De Smedt, Van Keer, & De Wever (2022), the result reveals the low to moderate argument skills after evaluating 130 argumentative text from the senior high school students. Additionally, a decline in argumentative skills of the students is observed after the reopening of classes after the pandemic.

B. Assumption Test

The findings of the study revealed the mean score of the students which is 53 which indicates “needs improvement”. This implies that almost half of students struggles with their assumption skills. They find it difficult to identify whether assumption is taken for granted and logically justified.

In the study of Aiyub, Suryadi, Fatimah, and Kusnandi (2021), the data they obtained shows that the students fail to understand the concept well and cannot bridge the information in relation to the question as a whole. The assumption skill of the students is low because the students are having hard time in understanding keywords contained in the questions. It can also be supported by the study of Fortus (2009), it reveals the students is having difficulty in making constraining assumptions and only the students who had prior experience were able to make assumptions and understand real world problems.

C. Deduction Test

The table above shows the mean score of the deduction test. It reveals the overall mean score of 73 which indicates “good”. This implies that almost 75 % of the students have good deduction skills. It signifies that the students can deduce information and reason logically in order to make a sound conclusion.

In the study of Kumar (2017), the deduction skills of the students is assessed and it reveals a high score. It enables students to draw valid conclusions, identify flaws in arguments, solve problems effectively, build knowledge, and communicate clearly. Mastering deduction give the students a powerful base for navigating the complexities of information and making well-informed decisions in a world full of ambiguity. The study of Hamad, Ahmed and Al (2021) reveals that the students excel at analyzing evidence and drawing well-supported conclusions. They can identify key indicators, differentiate between observations and inferences, and evaluate the validity of conclusions based on available data.

D. Interpretation Test

The results of the interpretation skills of the students revealed the mean score of 48 which indicates “poor”. It implies that majority of the students is struggling with their interpretation skills. It is difficult for the students to judge whether or not each of the proposed conclusions logically follows beyond a reasonable doubt from the information given in the paragraph.

The study of Hasanah, Sunarno, and Prayitno (2020) revealed that 46.87% of the students are categorized as low level in terms of critical thinking skills. Of the six critical thinking indicators, the interpretation indicators get the lowest average score, which is less than 40%. This is caused by several factors both from within the student (internal factor) and from the learning process (external factor). This finding is further supported by Yennita, Zulirfan, Irianti, Tukan, Ananda, & Naza (2023). The result of their

descriptive analysis revealed that the students' ability to interpret is in a low level category. This gives information to teachers that training and strengthening interpretation skills still need to be a concern. Henceforth, it is necessary to apply learning strategies to improve interpretation abilities.

E. Inference Test

The result revealed an overall score of 48 correct answers which indicates "poor". This implies that the students' inference skill is in need of improve due to its low mean score. The students' struggles to identify the inference or the conclusion is true and correct follows beyond a reasonable doubt.

The study of Kamsinah and Suryajaya (2020) reveals that only 25 % of students have good to better inference skills which signifies low category this is because students have not been able to identify the elements needed to settle conclusions and provide evidence of the truth of a statement or reasoning. The students that are still low indicate that the need for improvement of the learning process in the classroom.

F. Overall Result

The table 2 shows the overall mean scores of the different critical thinking tests namely: Assumption Test (52), Argument Test (53), Deduction Test (73), Interpretation Test (48), and Inference Test (48). It reveals the average score of 55 correct answers. It implies that the critical thinking skills of the students must be improved due to relatively low scores in the different part of the tests.

Senior high school students scored low in several aspects of critical thinking, including formulating problems, providing arguments, and analyzing results. The researchers suggest that argumentation-based learning could be a promising approach to improve critical thinking skills (Anggraeny, Said, & Febriani 2020)

Conclusions

The study aimed to study the level student's critical thinking ability using the Watson - Glaser appraisal specifically in the following dimension of critical thinking such as arguments, assumption, deductions, interpretations, and inferences.

The results revealed that the argument test scored 52 which means "needs improvement"; assumption test scored 53 means "needs improvement"; deduction test scored 73 means "good"; interpretation and inference test scored 48 which means "poor". Overall, the results indicated that the student's critical thinking ability requires relative improvement.

It is crucial to emphasize that the results does not dismiss the possibility that the respondents might inherently possess inadequate critical thinking skills, contributing to the overall difficulty experienced during the test. Further investigation into these factors

could provide valuable insights into improving educational strategies and addressing specific areas of difficulty for students.

Recommendations

Students' success both academically and personally depends on developing their critical thinking skills. These are some important tactics to think about. Initially, give open-ended questions in the classroom top priority. Asking "why" and "how" questions pushes students to go beyond mere recollection and instead examine material, recognize presumptions, and take into account other points of view. Socratic seminars and debate-style exercises work well to promote this kind of critical conversation.

Second, incorporate exercises that make students assess sources. Activities such as evaluating media bias, examining arguments for logical fallacies, and contrasting study approaches provide pupils the ability to separate fact from opinion or manipulation. Lastly, promote introspection and metacognition. Encourage pupils to reflect on their own prejudices, presumptions, and cognitive processes. Engaging in activities such as journaling about their experiences with learning or getting feedback from peers on their strengths and limitations in critical thinking can greatly aid in their development as more self-aware learners.

By putting these techniques into practice, teachers can enable their pupils to develop into critical thinkers who can competently negotiate the challenges of the twenty-first century.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study complied with all applicable ethical norms and regulations, which included getting participants' informed consent, protecting data confidentiality and anonymity, and refraining from any actions that would endanger or upset people. In addition, the research approach was transparent and objective, and the results were presented truthfully and impartially.

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